

Site: Sphinx temple Season 80

Area: N COLONNADE Square R 16 Locus Number (2) SURF.

Progress of Excavation REMOVAL of camel thorn + upper layer of modern debris (PLANT MATERIAL, PLASTIC, PAPERS etc.) ca. 05-20 cm deep. Matrix is a fairly loose medium-fine yellow sand mixed with decayed organic matter.

MATERIAL REMOVED NOT SCREENED + DUMPED.

Locus Description (see above)

Location in Square TO WEST of TALLEN CORE BLOCK RUNNING FROM EXPOSED PAVEMENT to N. WALL FACE of Temple

Under Locus _____ Over Locus _____

Locus Dimensions 2.70 m x 1.00

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____